

A Study on Emerging Trends in Tourism Industry in India

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Abstract

For centuries India has been a center of attraction for different people for different reasons in the outside world. The ancient invaders viewed it as a golden bird with abundant wealth accessible to plunder; the learned were fascinated by its mystic spiritualism and profound philosophy, the uninitiated saw it as a land of naked fakirs, snake-charmers, and rope-trick performers; while the others were simply charmed by the sheer beauty of its natural attraction and an amazing variety of its flora and fauna.

The Paper discusses the Indian tourism scenario, trends and development in the tourism market, various campaigns and new product development in India. Paper-based on secondary data to probe into the Government annual reports, newspapers, websites, published and non-published documents. This paper focuses on the tourism sector which is witnessing some new trends that are supplementing the established trends in the sector. These include solo trips, road trips, pocket-friendly traveling, and wellness tourism. These trends are expanding the horizon of the tourism industry in India and generating newer avenues for revenue creation.

In this industry, there are many competitors and, modern technology and hotel marketing trends, etc. This paper primarily aims and seeks to identify and examine the emerging trends in the industry and how India has behaved with the trends. It was however revealed that globally hospitality and tourism activities are increasing by leaps and bounds hence a proportionate increase in expenditure both for tourists and service providers.

Key Words: Tourism industry, Trends, New form, FEE.

Introduction

There are various definitions of tourism. *Theobald (1994)* suggested that etymologically, the word "tour" is derived from the Latin '*tornare*' and the Greek '*tornos*,' meaning '*a lathe or circle; the movement around a central point or axis.*'. The *Macmillan Dictionary* defines "*tourism as the business of providing services for people who are traveling for their holiday*". Wikipedia defines "*it as travel for recreational, leisure or business purposes*". The OECD glossary of statistical terms defined "*tourism as the activities of persons traveling to and staying in places outside their usual environment for not more than one consecutive year for leisure, business and other purposes not related to the exercise of an activity remunerated from within the place visited.*"

Earlier Travel – which was once considered as profligacy activity for high classes of the society, is now within the reach of billions. This has been possible with the lowering of travel barriers, falling costs, the growth of disposable income, the rise of middle-class and naturally – the changing attitude of the people towards travel in India. These factors have enabled the industry to flourish, so much by the 2nd decade of the 21st century.

There has been a huge change in the tourists as well as in tourism millennials. Now the all classes of societies especially the middle class which are known as budget tourists and developing economies taking the lead. This section of tourists and developing countries are having a hunger for new experience, knowledge and earning.

Tourism in India generated about 6.7% of the country's GDP in the year 2019 along with the millions of jobs about 8.1% of the total employment in India. New concepts and new trends in tourism and hospitality are getting huge attention from tourists. Even the government is also promoting these trends and supporting new entrepreneurs to implement their creativity in this industry. These new trends or millennials are supporting local economies of the

destinations throughout India and those destinations are creating the benchmark for sustainable development destinations like *Sikkim known as bamboo capital, organic state of India, Uttarakhand, and Kerala which are developing and promoting the concept of wellness and Yoga Tourism, Himachal Pradesh which is a well-known destination for adventure tourism, North-East states are working on Tribal culture and promoting their ethnicity, etc.*

Along with that hospitality, the segment is also developing various concepts that are becoming trends in this industry like using robots in the hotel, theme-based hotels, and accommodation, unconventional accommodations, etc.

Objectives of the Study

- To study about the emerging trends in India.
- To study the latest innovations and market share of the industry.
- To study the current scenario and the future of the tourism industry.

Research Methodology:

The present research paper is mostly based on secondary data sources. We have collected secondary data required for this paper from Reports of the Ministry of Tourism, Govt. of India 2019; India Tourism Statistics at a Glance 2018, Statistical Handbook of India, and other related information have been collected from the policy papers as well as research papers published in various journals. All collected data were analyzed with the help of trend line analysis.

Latest Tourism Trends in India

Tourism in India generated about 9.2% of the country's GDP in the year 2019 along with supporting 40.2 million jobs, which makes for about 8.7% of total employment. As of 2019, the future of tourism in India looks bright and prosperous because of the various favorable aspects of the country. With wonderful tourist spots, diverse topography, varied cultures and heritage sites in the country, India is one of the most lucrative options for tourists. The tourism industry of the country has undergone various changes over time. Some of the latest trends prevailing in the tourism industry are as follows:

1. Growing Options for Low Budget Travellers

With setups like hostels for travelers, various low budget options have come up recently in India. Numerous budget hotels, beds, and breakfast, and other such options are there to cater to the travelers, who are financially constrained. The taxes and other expenses for moving around the country are comparatively lower from other foreign destinations therefore it also becomes a good choice for budget travelers from around the globe.

Budget travel allows people to travel without being burdened by economic challenges. Budget travel options do not mean staying in shabby accommodations. It means planning the trip meticulously and setting a budget. One can search for online tips or conduct a plan themselves in order to have a perfect schedule. When one knows what one's budget is going to be like, planning a trip is easier. Planning well ahead can also give one some early bird incentives.

2. Robots, Chabot's and automation

One of the more eye-catching examples of these particular tourism trends is Connie, the Hilton Hotel chain's robot concierge. Other hotels have also got in on the robot-staff trend, installing interactive robots to handle certain reception duties or even having them serve food and drink to visitors. This kind of novelty application, however, is far from the only one. Many customers now book their travel and accommodation with the help of internet chatbots, specifically

tailored AI who can handle queries and assist customers with useful information when human operators are unavailable.

3. Artificial intelligence

As well as the aforementioned Chabot's, artificial intelligence is becoming increasingly important to the tourism industry. Machine learning technology is now firmly entrenched in the marketing of the tourism sector, with AI helping to personalize the experience of finding and booking tours and trips. AI is also increasingly valuable in contexts such as smart hotel rooms, identifying the likely needs of guests and fine-tuning the environment and services to fit the guest's needs and preferences. Artificial intelligence is finding applications everywhere, from customer service to security. Future AI tourism trends to watch out for might include self-driving vehicles and virtual guides for tourism.

4. Travel Blogging

Those who love to travel but do not have enough office holidays, whose passion is to visit new places but have an economic constraint, for them, taking up traveling as a profession might just work.

The new-age travel bloggers are doing exactly that and building their careers on it. A travel blogger can be a travel writer, a travel photographer or a videographer. They post their travel stories using various digital platforms. Once their pages start to become popular, they either get sponsorship or get paid through advertisements. Travel photographers often sell their photographs. Many travel writers are earning well by publishing their travel stories in several travel magazines also state governments and Tourism Development Corporation of Various states are using these bloggers to promote tourism.

*Ms. Honiya Dakpe known as **Indian Arunachali Gurl** a young traveler and renowned YouTuber from Arunachal Pradesh made her mark by being a culture promoter on YouTube. She is sharing hands with Govt of Arunachal Pradesh as a Brand Ambassador of State Campaign called **Hamara Arunachal Abhiyan Mission Ziro** which focuses on the promotion of aboriginal Culture, tribes, and ethnicity of Arunachal along with societal development points like women empowerment.*

Source:- <https://youtu.be/-wxg-YVhprU>
<https://youtu.be/2F-4gOsK0Pc>

Apart from her, there are various young travelers like **Nikhil Sharma from Mumbai**, who made his mark by being a lifestyle YouTuber. He earned well from his travel blogs. The blog '**Travel.See.Write.**' by **Archana Singh** is also quite popular. **ShivyaNath**, who has visited around 30 countries, has her blog called '**The Shooting Star**'. **Venkat Ganesh**, a motorbike-road-tripper, has named his blog as '**India Backpack Motorbike**'. **NeelimaVallangi**, who used to be a software engineer, left her job to be a travel blogger. Her blog '**The Wandering Soul's Wander Tale**' is enriched with exquisite photographs. There are many such travel bloggers and the trend is catching up fast.

5. Offbeat destinations/ less explored travel destinations:

India is a country that is largely diversified. There are so many places to visit, explore and travel. Travelers often look for some peace and relaxation. They look for a place that takes them away from their mundane routines. Exploring new destinations and spending vacations in lesser-known places is a gaining trend. The trend of offbeat tourism has also encouraged the industry to explore and expand its boundaries. Online travel platform '**MakeMyTrip**' sees offbeat tourism as a way of "treading less traveled path and visit unique places within India and around the world." They even provide elaborate information blogs promoting lesser-known destinations. In this era of social media, it is not unusual for obscure locations to gain

overnight popularity. Tourists start flowing in and the local tourism industry takes off. Some remarkable offbeat destinations are *Khajiar and Tirthan Valley of Himachal Pradesh, Ziro, Tawang, and Mechuka of Arunachal Pradesh, Chamber in Gujarat, Jhilimili and GarhPanchkot of West Bengal and Tranquebar of Tamil Nadu*. There are many other such places that are waiting to be explored and with this trend gaining traction, it can be expected that the tourism industry will expand to unlikely corners of India.

The Indian Tourism Industry is said to be the largest service providing industry in the nation. With the increase in its share over the past decade even places that were less explored have started to gain importance. The beauty and freshness of these areas drive the scores of tourists to visit them. Many of them are shoe the original-ancient Indian heritage while others pomp their wildlife and flora. The better network of roads and traveling facilities are also one of the major reasons behind this up soar.

6. Visa on Arrival Boosting Tourism

A bureaucratic and fast-growing country like India has a lot dependent on its government policies. Visa on arrival in India, which applies to tourists from over 40 countries, was started in 2014, since then a rise of foreign visitors has been observed. This policy is expected to be extended to more than 100 nationalities in the coming years.

7. Short weekend getaways

This is a prominent trend that is gaining popularity among a large section of new-age travelers. People are looking out for newer destinations for a short trip with minimum expenses. It is now much easier to travel as resources and connectivity have increased substantially. Today's travelers are increasingly looking for destinations within a 200-300 km radius and planning short vacations spanning across two to three days. With extended weekends, travel enthusiasts are increasingly making spontaneous plans to head out for nearby destinations for mini-vacations. Such short vacations are gaining momentum since it gives enough time to distress and rejuvenates oneself. Corporate houses are also planning such breaks in order to enhance the productivity of their often hackneyed employees. However, it is better to do a background check of these destinations as they are new and emerging. While traveling for longer vacations is always the favorite option heading out for week-ends is increasingly gaining popularity due to logistical and economic viability.

8. Rise of Boutique Hotels

A recent surge in the number of boutique hotels in the country has offered a wide variety of staying options for tourists. These boutique hotels provide comfort while letting the visitors indulge more into their surroundings, thus promoting tourism.

According to Justa's Founder and CEO, Ashish Vohra, "People travel to destinations such as Nathdwara or Chittorgarh to disengage with modern-world problems and connect with nature."

Jose Ramapuram, Director, Marketing, says "Through Evolve Back Luxury Resorts, we wish to capture people's new-found interest for untapped destinations and experiential travel. We choose a region where there is a potential for us to grow along with the destination itself."

Manu Rishi Guptha, CEO, Niraamaya told, "Boutique isn't about just being small and throwing together a few 'experiences'. It is an attitude to hospitality, which is unhurried and has a human face to it."

9. Solo trips

Modern life can throw its share of challenges. Increased stress and repetitiveness can lead individuals into distress. Solo travelers often reinvent themselves and their life goals by heading out for solo travel trips. Such trips are not merely meant to visit new places; it is also seen as a way to reconnect with one's soul and explore life goals. Solo travelers meet new

people, explore new places, overcome fears, and most significantly enjoy freedom by discovering themselves. Solo travelers can go anywhere. They are footloose in an exuberantly exclusive way.

India also has some popular solo traveling destinations. The *Srinagar-Leh road trip in the North-Western Himalayas* is popular among solo travelers. *Alleppey in Kerala and Kodaikanal in Tamil Nadu* are two other popular solo travel destinations. *Neha Kumari*, a solo traveler, and an IT professional told, "I have traveled in groups before. But I prefer solo trips because it gives me the independence and flexibility to travel and see places as I wish."

The concept of solo tourism is now being experimented with. Some travel companies are linking solo travelers and encouraging them to explore new destinations together. They are also facilitating solo trips. WOW Club has added their name to the list of companies that promote solo travel and is facilitating women solo travelers exclusively.

10. Poshtel Tourism

It is a combination of posh and hostel - and it's bringing together two concepts that most travelers wouldn't likely use together: luxury and hostel. This is one of the most trending forms of tourism in India and overseas. In the simplest ways, it can be called a **posh or luxurious hostel**. This makes it the best combination of both experience and price-wise. It comes easy on one's pockets but is as mesmerizing as a posh as a high rated hotel.

Many poshtels also offer facilities like bunker beds and a never-like before experience of living in a shared yet plush accommodation. These also add up to be the best option when traveling with a tour group.

11. Adventure Sports

The Indian tourism industry has in the recent past started exploring adventure sports and the Indian terrain highly supports the idea. Earlier Indians used to visit abroad for such thrill-seeking amusement but places like Sri Nagar, Manali, Bir Billing, Rishikesh, Panchmarhi Lonavala, Thekkady, Munnar, etc are a great destination for a fear-filled ecstasy.

Sports like camping, caving, kite surfing, water rafting, skiing, paragliding, mountain biking, scuba diving are just a few names out of the long list.

12. Travel Tradeshows Promoting Tourism

Travel tradeshows like SATTE, ITM, TTF, etc are working as a factor to promote tourism in India, by offering a platform for the various stakeholders in the country to showcase their services and products. It offers a combined place to them to have discussions over various policies, trends and how to improve its growth. If you are from the tourism industry, visiting the SATTE and other travel tradeshows can be quite beneficial.

The future of the Indian travel and tourism industry definitely looks bright with the latest trends prevailing.

13. Wellness tourism of India

The concept of wellness tourism has taken off in a big way in India. At places, it is often linked to spiritual tourism. The main reason for its gaining popularity is the immense work pressure of modern life. However, the trend is not completely new. It has been well-chronicled in Bengali literature and was popularly known as *hawabodol* or *change of air*. Doctors often suggested this to ailing patients and the popular destinations near Bengal like *Bankura and Purulia and other places in India like Ghatshila, Giridih* in Jharkhand, Rishikesh in Uttarakhand, Dharamshala in Himachal Pradesh, Ashtamundi in Kerala, etc. Even there are various accommodations establishments in India that are promoting and working on wellness tourism like *Shreyas Yoga Retreat, Bengaluru, Karnataka, Ananda in the Himalayas, Rishikesh, Uttarakhand, Sarovaram Ayurvedic Health Center, Ashtamudi, Kerala*, etc.

India has been ranked among the top 15 destinations for wellness tourism across Asia in 2015. The ancient healing art of Ayurveda has augmented wellness tourism. Kerala is a popular

destination for travelers seeking Ayurveda. Similarly, the ancient exercise form of Yoga attracts a large number of tourists to India.

Data Analysis

The analysis is done which based earnings from the tourism industry in India. The occupancy rate in hotels in India from FY 2001 to FY 2019 also gives an idea of the rise in the industry. The market share of passengers carried in domestic airlines across India also increases due to the trends in the industry.

The following is the data analysis with the interpretation:

Chart 1. Foreign exchange earnings from tourism in India from 2000 to 2018(in billion U.S. dollars)

Source: <https://www.statista.com/statistics/>

Interpretation: In 2018, foreign exchange earnings from the tourism industry across India amounted to over 28 billion U.S. dollars, an increase from the previous year. An exponential rise in the foreign exchange earnings was seen from 2009 in the country.

Chart 2. The occupancy rate in hotels in India from FY 2001 to FY 2019

Source: <https://www.statista.com/statistics/>

In the fiscal year 2019, the occupancy rate of hotels in India was 66.7 percent, up by one percent from the previous year. Among the various types of hotels, four-star hotels had the highest occupancy at 67.5 percent, making it the highest in this decade.

Chart 3. Market share of passengers carried in domestic airlines across India in FY 2018

Source: <https://www.statista.com/statistics/>

Interpretation: India's aviation sector had increasingly emerged as a fast-growing industry. The sector had established itself as an affordable and credible alternative to the tedious and long journeys via road or rail. With a visible growth trend, it was estimated that by 2034, India would become one of the largest aviation markets in the world. As of 2018, the passenger carrier IndiGo was the leader in the segment with nearly 40 percent in the market.

Conclusions

Tourism is not something new for India. India has an ancient tradition of tourism. The ancient rulers gave due recognition the travelers and created roads and many wayside facilities like inns, sarais, and dharmshalas for the benefit of tourists. A few centuries ago, the Mughal rulers built luxurious places and enchanting gardens in places of natural and scenic beauty. Creation of masterpiece Taj Mahal is today honor not in India, but abroad also is a symbol of India, was also built in Mughal times. After the Mughals, Britishers gave the new thrust and direction to the tourism in India. The establishment of Railways, construction of circuit houses, inspection bungalows, and forest rest houses provided adequate infrastructure facilities for luxury and wildlife tourism. At the same time, many hill stations in the Himalayas and other hill areas were developed by English people. In highlighting and discussing the major trends affecting the global tourist industry, it is inevitable to note that the majority of the factors tend to favor Asia. In essence, Asia is likely to emerge as the tourist hub of the world in the foreseeable future. Apart from these trends, there are other noticeable trends such as citizen-led initiatives wherein corporates work together with activists and citizen groups to promote sustainable tourism.

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